

REMODELING OF BRONCHIAL AND LUNG STRUCTURES IN EXPERIMENTAL BRONCHIECTASIS

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Abstract: Relevance. Bronchiectasis is a multifactorial disease often associated with chronic inflammation of the airways and recurrent infections. The relevance of studying bronchiectasis is due to its high prevalence in developing countries, especially among children, and the difficulty of diagnosing it in the early stages. Research on bronchiectasis in laboratory animals allows for a deeper understanding of the cellular and molecular mechanisms of the disease, which is crucial for developing new diagnostic and treatment methods, particularly in settings with limited access to medical care.

Objective: The aim of the study was to investigate the structural changes in the bronchial walls of different calibers and lungs during the progression of experimental bronchiectasis in laboratory rabbits.

Materials and Methods: The study utilized the bronchi and lungs of 46 adult rabbits. Morphological, morphometric, and statistical methods were employed to assess the morphofunctional changes in the bronchi and lungs. The modeling of bronchiectasis was conducted by introducing a nylon thread into the trachea. The animals were observed for 3, 4, 5, and 6 months, after which they were sacrificed under anesthesia. For analysis, the tissues were stained using hematoxylin and eosin, Van Gieson's picric acid fuchsin, Weigert's resorcin-fuchsin, and Masson's trichrome staining methods, along with statistical analysis.

Results: In the exudative stage of inflammation in experimental bronchiectasis, inflammatory and destructive processes develop in the bronchi and lungs of experimental animals. The proliferative stage of bronchiectasis in rabbits is characterized by significant thickening of all structural layers of the bronchial walls, indicating the progression of inflammation and its transition to a chronic form. These changes suggest serious morphological alterations leading to impaired respiratory function and the development of fibrosis.

Conclusion: In the exudative stage of experimental bronchiectasis, bronchial wall thickening and increased inflammation occur, leading to destructive changes. The proliferative stage is marked by the progression of inflammation and the development of fibrosis.

Keywords: Experimental bronchiectasis, rabbits, metaplasia.

Relevance. Bronchiectasis is a multifactorial disease associated with other conditions. According to the literature, the most common causes of bronchiectasis include previous pneumonia (19%), primary immunodeficiency (17%), recurrent aspiration, including inhalation of foreign bodies (10%), and primary ciliary dyskinesia (7%). Additionally, 30% of cases remain idiopathic (1,13,14).

Chronic inflammation of the airways is the primary cause of bronchiectasis, which arises from recurrent lung infections. Bronchiectasis is a multifactorial condition involving complex interactions between the body, respiratory pathogens, and environmental factors (6,8,11). These interactions create a vicious cycle of infections, inflammation, tissue remodeling, and destruction of bronchial wall structures. The exact timing of bronchiectasis development is difficult to determine due to the late confirmation of the diagnosis. Data on the prevalence of the disease vary by geographic region. In developed countries, the incidence among children aged 0-14 years is low; for example, in Finland, it is 0.5 per 100,000 children, and in New Zealand, it is 3.7 per 100,000 children. Among Aboriginal children in Central Australia, the incidence can reach 200 per 100,000 children (2,5). In India, the incidence of bronchiectasis ranges from 212 to 2,646 cases per 1 million children per year, due to inadequate post-pneumonia medical care for children under 4 years old (1,12,13). Studies on the prevalence of bronchiectasis among children in Russia have not been conducted. According to ICD-10 codes J44 (other chronic obstructive pulmonary disease) and J47 (bronchiectasis), statistical data on the prevalence of diseases among children aged 0 to 14 years show 98.3 cases per 100,000 children in 2010 and 89.3 cases in 2011. Thus, bronchiectasis remains a serious problem for vulnerable populations, particularly children living in developing countries, due to population density, poor sanitation, and limited access to medical services in these areas (3,5,7,10).

The etiology of bronchiectasis has been identified in 60% of cases, including post-infectious causes (20%), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (15%), connective tissue diseases (10%), immunodeficiency (5.8%), and asthma (3.3%). In 13% of cases, the identified etiology led to changes in patient management (6). Nearly one-third of patients with uncontrolled moderate to severe asthma are found to have bronchiectasis. Bronchiectasis is associated with the severity of asthma, the presence of chronic sputum, a history of prior pneumonia, and low levels of FeNO (4,9,14).

Analysis of lung tissue in bronchiectasis in laboratory animals plays a key role in studying the cellular and molecular mechanisms of chronic respiratory diseases, and it contributes to the development of innovative approaches to diagnosis and therapy.

Objective. The aim of the study was to investigate the structural changes in the bronchial walls of different calibers and the lungs during the progression of experimental bronchiectasis in rabbits.

Materials and Methods. The study involved the bronchi and lungs of 46 adult rabbits weighing between 2.5 to 3 kg. Of these, 36 rabbits underwent experimental pneumonia, and 10 served as the control group. Morphological, morphometric, and statistical methods were used to assess morphofunctional changes in the bronchial walls and lung tissues under experimental conditions. Bronchiectasis was modeled by introducing a nylon thread into the trachea. A pneumonia model was selected for the experiment, which was induced in the laboratory animals using a modification of the method by M.I. Zakharyevskaya and N.I. Anichkov. The dynamics of the inflammatory process were monitored, and the animals were studied 3, 4, 5, and 6 months after the operation, with 8-9 animals in each group. The animals were sacrificed under anesthesia with Telazol (20 mg/kg) followed by severing the abdominal aorta. The care and sacrifice of the laboratory animals were conducted in strict compliance with the bioethical standards established for experimental research in the Republic of Uzbekistan. For the analysis of the obtained material, we used hematoxylin and eosin staining, Van Gieson's picric acid fuchsin, Weigert's resorcin-fuchsin, and Masson's trichrome staining methods, along with statistical analysis.

Results. Three months after inducing experimental bronchiectasis, pronounced alterative-exudative processes were observed in the respiratory system of the laboratory animals. Macroscopically, mucopurulent contents were found in the bronchial cavities, the lungs appeared mottled, and areas of atelectasis and distelctasis were detected. Additionally, mucopurulent contents were observed draining from some peribronchial areas upon incision.

Microscopically, in the mucous membrane of the large and medium-sized bronchi, destructive-desquamative changes were noted in the cells of the pseudostratified ciliated epithelium. Cilia were observed to be clumped together, with localized necrosis of columnar cells. Goblet cells were hypertrophied and filled with secretions. The submucosal layer was infiltrated with lymphocytes, segmented neutrophils, fibrocytes, fibroblasts, plasma cells, and macrophages. Inflammatory cell infiltration was also detected in the respiratory part of the lungs (Fig. 1). Lymphocytic infiltration extended between epithelial cells and sometimes reached their surfaces.

Fig. 1. Macrophage infiltration in the cavity of small bronchi. Hemostasis in small blood vessels and infiltration of interstitial lung tissue with lymphocytes, neutrophils, and fibrocytes. Hematoxylin and eosin staining. Magnification X400.

At 6 months, a reduction in lung volume was observed in the rabbits. Macroscopically, the lung tissue appeared collapsed, with small areas of emphysema. Some animals exhibited encapsulated abscesses and adhesions with the parietal pleura. The walls of the trachea and bronchi were thickened, and pus was present in the tracheal lumen and on the surface of the thread.

Microscopic analysis revealed focal hyperplasia and metaplasia of the epithelium in the large bronchi, with the formation of papillary outgrowths (Fig. 2). The bronchial walls were also thickened and infiltrated with lymphocytes and neutrophils. Picrinophilia and focal sclerosis of connective tissue were observed (Fig. 3). In the interalveolar septa, capillaries protruded into the lumen and had distinct outlines. Neutrophils, lymphocytes, and macrophages were present in the respiratory section, along with signs of vasculitis. Foci of abscess organization contained large cellular elements.

Fig. 2. Metaplasia of the pseudostratified ciliated epithelium of a medium-caliber bronchus into stratified non-keratinizing epithelium. Pronounced edema of the submucosa beneath the metaplastic epithelium of the medium-caliber bronchus. Hematoxylin and eosin staining. Magnification X400.

Fig. 3. Picrinophilia of collagen fibers in the lamina propria of small bronchi and collagen fibers in the interglandular septa. Van Gieson staining. Magnification X400.

During the analysis of histological sections using morphometric methods, the following changes were observed in the experimental group of rabbits during the exudative stage of inflammation.

On the 90th day of the experiment, a significant increase in the thickness of the mucosa and other structural layers of the bronchial walls was observed in the rabbits. In the large bronchi, the thickness of the mucosa reached $69.6 \pm 1.9 \mu\text{m}$, which significantly exceeds the normal value. The PO MRE indicator reached $87.2 \pm 1.6 \mu\text{m}$, the thickness of the fibrous-cartilaginous and muscular layer was $263.7 \pm 1.5 \mu\text{m}$, and the thickness of the adventitial layer was $12.6 \pm 1.7 \mu\text{m}$.

In the medium bronchi, on the 90th day of the experiment, the mucosal thickness increased to $54.3 \pm 1.4 \mu\text{m}$. The PO MRE indicator was $85.1 \pm 1.4 \mu\text{m}$, the thickness of the fibrous-cartilaginous and muscular layer reached $223.2 \pm 1.6 \mu\text{m}$, and the adventitial layer had a thickness of $11.4 \pm 1.4 \mu\text{m}$.

In the small bronchi, a thickening of the mucosa to $41.5 \pm 1.7 \mu\text{m}$ was also recorded, the PO MRE indicator was $73.4 \pm 1.4 \mu\text{m}$, and the thickness of the fibrous-cartilaginous and muscular layer (F-C/MO) was $212.4 \pm 1.7 \mu\text{m}$. These indicators suggest significant thickening of the bronchial walls by the 90th day of the experiment, indicating progressive pathological changes in the airways.

These data indicate pronounced structural changes in the bronchi associated with the inflammatory process.

The proliferative stage is characterized by significant and progressive changes in the bronchial and lung tissues, indicating the transition of the inflammatory process to a chronic form with pronounced tissue remodeling. At this stage, observed 5 months after the onset of the disease, there is a marked thickening of the bronchial mucosa across all calibers. In the large bronchi, the mucosal thickness increases to $79.6 \pm 1.8 \mu\text{m}$, which is significantly higher compared to the previous stages, indicating an intensification of the inflammatory process. During the proliferative stage, there is an increase in the submucosal layer of the pseudostratified ciliated epithelium, reflecting epithelial cell proliferation and structural changes in the bronchial epithelium. The maximum values are reached by the 5th month: $89.3 \pm 1.8 \mu\text{m}$ for large bronchi, $86.4 \pm 1.3 \mu\text{m}$ for medium bronchi, and $76.3 \pm 1.7 \mu\text{m}$ for small bronchi.

Additionally, the proliferative stage is characterized by significant thickening of the fibrous-cartilaginous and muscular layers of the bronchi. In the large bronchi, the thickness of these layers reaches $275.1 \pm 1.9 \mu\text{m}$, which greatly exceeds the measurements observed during the exudative stage.

The proliferative stage also shows an increase in the thickness of the adventitial layer, particularly in the large bronchi, where this parameter reaches $15.1 \pm 1.4 \mu\text{m}$ by the 5th month. This suggests the spread of inflammation to the outer layers of the bronchial walls and the possible involvement of surrounding tissues.

Compared to the control group, on the 180th day of the experiment, rabbits in the proliferative stage of experimental bronchiectasis exhibited a significant increase in the thickness of the mucosa and other layers of the bronchial walls. For example, the mucosal thickness in large bronchi was 87.7 μm , which is 1.54 times greater than in the control group. The thickness of the submucosal layer of the pseudostratified ciliated epithelium exceeded that of the mucosa. In large bronchi, the thickness of the submucosal layer was 90.2 μm , which is 1.16 times greater than in the control group. This is associated with inflammatory cell infiltration, hemostasis in the microcirculatory bed, and hypertrophy of the bronchial glands.

When measuring the percentage of inflammatory cells in the walls of bronchi of different calibers and the respiratory section of the lungs, the following changes were observed.

From day 90 to day 180 of the observation, an increase in the percentage of cellular content was noted in the bronchial walls of various calibers and the respiratory section of the lungs in experimental animals compared to normal values. Lymphocytes increased by 0.51 times in the third month and by 0.31 times in the sixth month, reaching 18.46%. Macrophages increased by 0.31 times in the third month and by 0.18 times in the sixth month, reaching 16.48%. Neutrophils increased by 0.46 times in the third month and by 0.32 times in the sixth month, reaching 43.6%. Plasmablasts and plasma cells increased by 0.15 times in the third month and by 0.12 times in the sixth month, reaching 16.84%. Fibrocytes and fibroblasts increased by 0.24 times in the third month and by 0.15 times in the sixth month, reaching 26.84% in large bronchi. In medium-sized bronchi, on the sixth month of the experiment, there was an increase in lymphocytes by 0.33, macrophages by 0.46, neutrophils by 0.44, plasmablasts and plasma cells by 0.16, and fibrocytes and fibroblasts by 0.22 times. Meanwhile, on the sixth month, the number of lymphocytes and macrophages increased by 0.29 times, neutrophils by 0.31 times, plasmablasts and plasma cells by 0.14, and fibrocytes and fibroblasts by 0.16 times compared to the control group. In small bronchi, the cellular composition increased as follows: lymphocytes by 0.31 times on the sixth month, and by 0.28 times over the entire six-month period; macrophages increased by 0.49 to 0.27 times; neutrophils by 0.34 to 0.24 times; plasma cells and plasmablasts by 0.087 to 0.08 times; fibrocytes and fibroblasts by 0.20 to 0.15 times. Significant infiltrates of inflammatory cells were also recorded in the respiratory section, which increased as follows compared to the control group: lymphocytes and macrophages by 0.36 to 0.53 times, neutrophils by 0.25 to 0.22 times, plasmablasts and plasma cells by 0.008 to 0.006 times, and fibroblasts and fibrocytes by 0.07 to 0.06 times.

The proliferative stage of experimental bronchiectasis is accompanied by a significant increase in fibrotic changes, reflected in the thickening of the fibrous-cartilaginous and muscular layers. These changes indicate remodeling of bronchial tissue and the possible formation of scar tissue, which is a characteristic feature of chronic inflammation.

Conclusion. In the exudative stage of inflammation in experimental bronchiectasis, thickening of all layers of the bronchial walls and an increase in the number of inflammatory cells are observed, indicating the development of inflammatory and destructive processes in the bronchi and lungs of experimental animals. The proliferative stage of bronchiectasis in rabbits is characterized by significant thickening of all structural layers of the bronchial walls, indicating the progression of inflammation and its transition to a chronic form. The increase in the thickness of the mucosa, submucosa, fibrous-cartilaginous and muscular layers, as well as the adventitial layer, points to serious morphological changes leading to impaired respiratory function and the development of fibrosis.

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